

DELIVERABLE D4.2

GUIDELINES FOR ACCESSING HTA SERVICES

WP4 – Long-term Sustainability Planning

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One of the main aims of EATRIS-Plus project is to expand EATRIS's catalogue of services to better support the research community, as well as ensure the organisation's sustainability. In this light Task 4.3: *Expand catalogue of services: the setting up of EATRIS Health Technology Assessment (HTA) Task Force* in WP4 – Long-term Sustainability Planning is contributing to this goal from the Health Technology Analysis perspective. Within this task the **Deliverable 4.2: Guidelines for accessing HTA services** describes the specific details of the service.

DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

BACKGROUND

Given the development of complex health related technologies, the assessment of potential benefits and their related costs becomes increasingly important. It is crucial to understand the overall effects in terms of safety, clinical effectiveness, economic sustainability, ethical aspects, organisational impact, social and legal aspects to fully understand their value for patients and society overall. The assessment of the consequences related with the adoption of a new health technology should therefore include a multidimensional approach, typical of Health Technology Assessment (HTA), and the involvement of a multi-disciplinary team. For this reason, it is often not possible to perform such analysis within an organization and the support of a wide network of experts is required. The opportunity to access HTA related services is offered by EATRIS with the support of professionals with consolidated experience.

The main aim of such a service is to support the developers of health technologies and financing entities to highlight critical issues and benefits related with the implementation and development of the technologies, as well as gaps in the information required to conduct a complete assessment, to help them to implement new studies or to revise ongoing studies to fill those gaps.

The service is primarily meant for funding organisations, research teams that deal with the development of health technologies, and companies implementing health technologies solutions.

The experts within EATRIS community contributing to this service vary according to the context of investigation and the domains of interest. Similar approach is taken with the price, the cost depends on the type of analysis required (early assessment, headroom type analysis, rapid HTA or full HTA) and on the number of domains investigated.

4 main types of services provided are early HTA, headroom type analyses, rapid HTA and full HTA.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

HTA Capacity Analysis

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) capacities mapping exercise was performed among EATRIS Institutions in early 2021. The questionnaire was developed starting from a literature review performed through the biomedical scientific literature search engine PubMed. The questionnaire was implemented considering the items reported in the EUnetHTA Handbook on HTA capacity building and revised according to the objective of the investigation.

The questionnaire is composed by four main parts, subdivided into 9 sections. The first part of the document concern general and contact information. The second part of the questionnaire investigates the activities performed by the institution in terms of assessment of health technologies and the collaborations established with external entities and supportive material.

Furthermore, information is collected on the training (if any) offered for the assessment of health technologies to the staff of the organization, on which areas and on the type of training.

Finally, it is enquired whether the results of the assessments conducted are published at any level, if the institution offers services for the assessment of health technologies (and which ones), and which are (if any), according to the respondent, the limitations to the implementation of the assessment of health technologies within the institution.

Among the 100 questionnaires sent to the centers collaborating with EATRIS 10 completed the questionnaires by the time of this report. This low number of respondents could be attributed to the fact that most institutions within EATRIS community are academic centers and these types of institutions do not perform a lot of HTAs. In addition, the questionnaire was open to respondents for 2 months by the time of this report.

These 10 Institutions are equally distributed between centers that conduct HTAs and centers that do not conduct HTAs, while the large majority of them (90%), perceive as important to conduct such assessment. The full results of the capacities mapping can be found in Annex 1.

HTA Service Access Guidelines

In conjunction with the results of the capacities mapping effort, the guidelines for accessing EATRIS's HTA services were developed. The aim of the guidelines is to raise awareness that EATRIS is providing this service, as well as streamline the incoming requests regarding this service.

These can be found in Annex 2 and will be posted to EATRIS Website by May/ June 2021 in conjunction with the general website restructuring.

NEXT STEPS

1. HTA Service Access Guidelines will be posted to EATRIS website
2. The HTA Capacity Mapping survey became a part of the EATRIS Platforms survey that allows for any existing and new EATRIS institutions to edit their information or complete the survey at any point in time using their institutional token. This will ensure the sustainability of the effort and a better overview of EATRIS Institutions' capacities.
3. Assembly of the HTA Task Force – experts from institutions with relevant expertise will be invited to join the HTA task force formed by EATRIS. The task force will closely monitor recent policy

developments towards increased harmonisation of HTA frameworks among EU member states, engage with relevant ongoing projects, as well as early dialogue with patients. Task force participants will explore possibilities to offer HTA support for research grant applicants in collaboration with funders and charities, with the support of WP5 – Stakeholder Engagement.

ABBREVIATIONS

HTA – Health Technology Assessment

DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

The activities were performed by the foreseen due date April 30th 2021, the deliverable was submitted with a delay of 2 working days by May 4th 2021.

ADJUSTMENTS MADE

n/a

APPENDICES

Annex 1 – HTA Capacity Survey Results

Annex 2 – HTA Service Access Guidelines

HTA capacities mapping

Objective

The objective of the capacities mapping activity conducted is to assess the capacities related to Health Technology Assessment (HTA) within the centers collaborating with EATRIS through a questionnaire.

Methodology

The questionnaire was developed starting from a literature review performed through the biomedical scientific literature search engine PubMed.

The keywords used for the search were: Health Technology Assessment, HTA, Technology Assessment, capacity, capacities, expertise, mapping. The search string was: (((("health technology assessment") OR (hta) OR ("technology assessment"))) AND ((capacity) OR (capacities) OR (expertise)) AND (mapping))).

Due to the low number of results, a further search was performed considering less restrictive keywords, as follow: (((("health technology assessment") OR (hta) OR ("technology assessment"))) AND (mapping))).

An additional search was performed through the website of the European Network for Health Technology Assessment (EUnetHTA) and through a generic web search engine.

Most of the documents found did not consider the capacity mapping topic, being related to capacity building or to the mapping of existing HTA organisations. However, the questionnaires and information presented within the selected documents, were considered to implement a questionnaire to identify the capacities related to HTA within the centers collaborating with EATRIS.

The articles and reports considered are listed below:

- de Labry Lima AO, Mochon LG, Martínez AC, Ruiz EM, Balbino JE. Mapping Capacity to Conduct Health Technology Assessment in Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe. *Croat Med J.* 2016 Feb;57(1):66-70.
- Oortwijn W, Broos P, Vondeling H, Banta D, Todorova L. Mapping of Health Technology Assessment in Selected Countries. *Int J Technol Assess Health Care.* 2013 Oct;29(4):424-34.
- Chamova J. Mapping of HTA national organisations, programmes and processes in EU and Norway. European Commission - Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety. May 2017.
- EUnetHTA Work Package 8. EUnetHTA Handbook on Health Technology Assessment Capacity Building. Barcelona (Spain): Catalan Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Research. Catalan Health Service. Department of Health Autonomous Government of Catalonia; 2008.
- Moharra M, Kubesch N, Estrada MD, Parada A, Cortés M, Espallargues M on behalf of Work Package 8, EUnetHTA project. Survey report on HTA organisations. Barcelona (Spain): Catalan Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Research. Catalan Health Service. Department of Health. Autonomous Government of Catalonia; May 2008.

The questionnaire was implemented considering the items reported in the EUnetHTA Handbook on HTA capacity building and revised according to the objective of the investigation. The questionnaire was integrated with criteria included in the article written by Oortwijn et al. (2013) and the indications presented in Chamova et al. (2017), de Labry Lima et al. (2016) and Moharra et al. (2008).

The final step was the revision and integration of the items considered with the domains reported within the EunetHTA HTA Core Model[®] (Version 3.0), in order to map the capacities within the centers considered, to be able to evaluate each domain to be included in an HTA.

The questionnaire is composed by four main parts, subdivided into 9 sections.

The first part of the document concern general and contact information.

The second part of the questionnaire investigates the activities performed by the institution in terms of assessment of health technologies and the collaborations established with external entities and supportive material. The section is willing to understand whether the institution perform assessment activities related to health technologies, which kind of technologies are assessed, the number of assessments conducted on a yearly basis and whether the center perceive as important this kind of activity and if there is a specific budget allocated at an institutional level.

In case the assessment of health technologies is conducted, the composition of the team that conduct such activity (considering the background of the components to understand for which domains there might be a specific know-how) and which aspects are considered are investigated.

Considering the possibility to implement or to widen the type of assessments conducted, information regarding the following aspects are considered: 1) the type of entities with which the institution has established active collaborations, 2) the type of background of the professionals working within the institution, as well as external collaborators, and whether they have experience in the field of HTA, 3) the databases to which the institution has active access to.

Furthermore, information is collected on the training (if any) offered for the assessment of health technologies to the staff of the organization, on which areas and on the type of training.

Finally, it is enquired whether the results of the assessments conducted are published at any level, if the institution offers services for the assessment of health technologies (and which ones), and which are (if any), according to the respondent, the limitations to the implementation of the assessment of health technologies within the institution.

Results

Among the 100 questionnaires sent by EATRIS to its collaborating centers 10 filled questionnaires were received. The questionnaire has been open to respondents for 2 months by the time of this report.

Concerning general and contact information, data related to institution type, country and respondent position have been collected. Institutions are equally divided between research institutes (5) and universities (5), located in Spain (5), Portugal (2), Italy (1), Slovenia (1) and The Netherlands (1). The roles of the respondents are: directors/administrators (managing and scientific directors or coordinators, university directors), technology transfer managers, coordinator of healthcare quality and clinical excellence unit, professors (and deans).

Graphics related with the aforementioned information are reported below.

Figure 1. Institution type among respondents

Figure 2. Countries in which responding institutions are located

The following questions were considered to investigate aspects related to HTA activities:

1. Does your institution conduct assessment of health technologies (i.e. before their implementation in the institution)?
 - a. Do you perceive it as important to conduct such assessment?
 - b. Which kind of health technologies have been assessed so far?
 - c. What is the mean number of assessments performed yearly?

- d. Is there a budget allocated to conduct assessments of health technologies?
- e. Is there a team established to conduct the assessment of health technologies?
- f. Please specify the background of the TEAM MEMBERS conducting HTAs at your institution.

Institutions are equally distributed between centers that conduct HTAs and centers that are not conducting HTAs, while the large majority of them, equal to 90%, perceive as important to conduct such assessment.

Figure 3. Institutions that conduct assessment of health technologies

The majority of institutions (90%) perceive HTAs importance to evaluate benefits and critical aspects in a preliminary phase of the implementation.

Figure 4. Institutions that perceive the assessment of health technologies as important

Most of the centers that are not conducting complete HTAs specify that they conduct different types of evaluations such as economic evaluations, pharmacotherapeutic evaluations, budget impact analyses, adequacy, safety and cost-effectiveness evaluations.

Within centers that are conducting HTAs 100% assess diagnostic technologies, 80% medical devices and clinical and diagnostic procedures, 40% assess health programmes and 20% pharmaceuticals.

Figure 5. Type of health technologies assessed

Concerning the mean number of assessments performed yearly they varies from 1 to (at least) 4.

Figure 6. Mean number of assessments of health technologies performed per year

Sixty percent of respondents have a budget allocated to conduct assessments of health technologies and a team established to conduct them.

Figure 7. Presence of a budget allocated to conduct assessment of health technologies

Figure 8. Presence of a team to conduct assessment of health technologies

Some centers state that specific units, especially concerning quality, are involved in conducting the assessments.

The background of the team members conducting HTAs is varied but the majority include clinical specialist, experts and health service researchers.

Figure 9. Number of professionals involved in the assessment of health technologies

Figure 10. Background of the members of the teams conducting assessment of health technologies

Concerning professionals involved in HTAs from outside the organization the following questions have been included in the questionnaire:

2. Background of professionals outside of your organisation you are collaborating with.
 - a. Which type of entities has your institution established active collaborations with?
 - b. Responses are reported with the total value and are also divided between centers that are conducting HTA and centers that are not conducting HTA.

The majority of respondents state that their institutions are collaborating with external experts as clinical specialists, economists and legal experts. More than 50% of centers conducting HTAs involve from 2 to 5 external experts being health service researchers and legal experts, while more than 50% of centers not conducting HTAs involve from 1 to 16 external experts, being clinical specialists, economists and media professionals. One respondent specifies that also external senior scientists, pharmacologists and project managers are involved in the institution activities. Data plot reflect the

total number of responses (total) and the relative distribution between those conducting or not conducting HTA.

Figure 11. Background of the external professionals with whom entities are collaborating with (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Figure 12. Number of external collaborators with whom the entities are collaborating with (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Concerning collaborating entities, more than 50% of respondents state that their institution is collaborating with industries, hospitals, governmental agencies and academies/universities (medicine faculties). Centers conducting HTAs collaborate with 2 to 6 entities, while centers not conducting HTAs collaborate with 2 to 11 entities.

Figure 13. Type of collaborating entities with whom institutions are collaborating with (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Figure 14. Number of collaborating entities with whom institutions are collaborating with (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

The following question has been included concerning the publication of results of the assessments conducted:

3. Are the results of the assessments conducted published in report or scientific articles?

The majority of respondents, equal to 80%, states that the results of the assessments conducted are published in report or scientific articles, one respondent specify that documents are published only within the institution.

Figure 15. Publication of the results of the assessments conducted (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Concerning the main limitations in the implementation of the assessment of health technologies the following question was reported in the questionnaire:

4. What are the main limitations in the implementation of the assessment of health technologies within your institution?

The majority of respondents identified 1 limitation. Main limitations are related to lack of human resources and lack of knowledge while a large part of centers that are not conducting HTAs highlights as major limitation the lack of funding. Centers specify that “others” indicate that there are no major limitations.

Figure 16. Limitations in the implementation of the assessment (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

The following question was considered to assess if the assessment of health technologies is compulsory for public entities within national/regional contexts:

5. Is the assessment of health technologies compulsory for public entities within your national / regional context?

The majority of respondent reported that the assessment of health technologies is not compulsory for public entities within the national/regional context.

Figure 17. Is the assessment of health technology compulsory? (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Concerning the services related to the assessment of health technologies for external users the following questions have been included in the questionnaire:

6. Is your institution offering services related to the assessment of health technologies for external users?
 - a. In which area of expertise, among the following?

Sixty percent of centers that are conducting HTAs are offering services related to the assessment of health technologies for external users, while 60% of centers that are not conducting HTAs are not offering these services. The majority of respondents indicate that the main areas of expertise of services related to the assessment of health technologies for external users are safety, efficacy/effectiveness followed by service requirements/organisational implications, medical practice patterns, economic implications (budget impact - sustainability of the investment), patient preferences and economic evaluations (efficiency in resources allocation - cost-effectiveness, cost-utility, cost-benefit). Centers specify that “others” can be human factors, usability and pharmacotherapeutic evaluations. The areas of expertise of centers conducting HTAs range from 0 to 5, while the ones of centers not conducting HTAs range from 0 to 6.

Figure 18. Services offered related to the assessment of health technologies for external users (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Figure 19. Areas of expertise of services related to the assessment of health technologies for external users (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

The following question has been included concerning the information sources available:

7. Which of the following information sources available in your institution?

The majority of respondents (90%) indicate that Web of Knowledge is available in the institution, 70% indicate Scopus. Also, within centers that are conducting HTAs the main information sources available are Scopus and Web of Knowledge.

Figure 20. Information sources available (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Concerning training activities, the following questions were proposed in the questionnaire:

8. Are training activities performed for staff to conduct assessments of health technologies?
 - a. Which area of expertise, among the following are the training activities performed in?
 - b. How is the training performed, among the following options?

The majority of respondents are not performing training activities for staff to conduct assessments of health technologies, while 30% of respondents state that this type of training is performed. The main area of expertise for training activities is clinical (efficacy/effectiveness, safety), while concerning methods of training most centers indicate the inclusion of multiple methods, as formal external, formal internal and informal.

Figure 21. Training activities performed for staff to conduct assessments of health technologies (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Figure 22. Areas of expertise for training (“Total” refers to the whole sample)

Conclusion

Data shows that not all centers are autonomous in carrying out HTA activities due to different types of limitations, although the majority of the respondent institutions highlight its importance. The interests in the assessment are various and, therefore, also teams and entities with which the institutions collaborate with vary.

There is also an interest in publishing the results of the assessments conducted, even if the national or regional non-compulsory nature of this activity.

Finally, it is noted that some of the centers offer their own HTA services to external users in different areas of expertise though most institutions are not offering training activities to staff to conduct assessments of health technologies.

References

- 1) de Labry Lima AO, Mochon LG, Martínez AC, Ruiz EM, Balbino JE. Mapping Capacity to Conduct Health Technology Assessment in Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe. *Croat Med J.* 2016 Feb;57(1):66-70.
- 2) Oortwijn W, Broos P, Vondeling H, Banta D, Todorova L. Mapping of Health Technology Assessment in Selected Countries. *Int J Technol Assess Health Care.* 2013 Oct;29(4):424-34.
- 3) Chamova J. Mapping of HTA national organisations, programmes and processes in EU and Norway. European Commission - Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety. May 2017.
- 4) EUnetHTA Work Package 8. EUnetHTA Handbook on Health Technology Assessment Capacity Building. Barcelona (Spain): Catalan Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Research. Catalan Health Service. Department of Health Autonomous Government of Catalonia; 2008.
- 5) Moharra M, Kubesch N, Estrada MD, Parada A, Cortés M, Espallargues M on behalf of Work Package 8, EUnetHTA project. Survey report on HTA organisations. Barcelona (Spain): Catalan Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Research. Catalan Health Service. Department of Health. Autonomous Government of Catalonia; May 2008.
- 6) EUnetHTA Joint Action 2, Work Package 8. HTA Core Model[®] version 3.0 (Pdf); 2016. Available from www.htacoremodel.info/BrowseModel.aspx.

Title: Health Technology Assessment Service

Short description:

Given the development of complex health related technologies, the assessment of potential benefits and their related costs becomes increasingly important. It is crucial to understand the overall effects in terms of safety, clinical effectiveness, economic sustainability, ethical aspects, organisational impact, social and legal aspects to fully understand their value for patients and society overall. The assessment of the consequences related with the adoption of a new health technology should therefore include a multidimensional approach, typical of Health Technology Assessment (HTA), and the involvement of a multi-disciplinary team. For this reason, it is often not possible to perform such analysis within an organization and the support of a wide network of experts is required. The opportunity to access HTA related services is offered by EATRIS with the support of professionals with consolidated experience.

What is the aim:

To support the developers of health technologies and financing entities to highlight critical issues and benefits related with the implementation and development of the technologies, as well as gaps in the information required to conduct a complete assessment, to help them to implement new studies or to revise ongoing studies to fill those gaps.

Who is it for:

Funding organisations, research teams that deal with the development of health technologies, companies implementing health technologies solutions.

Who are the experts:

The experts vary according to the context of investigation and the domains of interest.

What does it cost:

The cost depends on the type of analysis required (early assessment, headroom type analysis, rapid HTA or full HTA) and on the number of domains investigated.

What services are provided:

Early HTA, headroom type analyses, rapid HTA and full HTA.

Testimonies

“As a charity, Prinses Beatrix Spierfonds and its fellow funders support high impact research and development to find novel treatments and to improve the quality of life of patients with muscle disorders. The translational assessment performed in 2019 by EATRIS as an independent party was very useful in making an informed decision to provide financial support to Yumen Bionics that develops an innovative bionic arm to improve the quality of life of Duchenne patients. The early Health Technology Assessment and the SWOT analysis performed by an international panel of clinical and HTA experts provided valuable insights.”

Ellen Sterrenburg, Policy and Research Manager, Prinses Beatrix Spierfonds

“As a small company focused on rare diseases, we are relying on collaborations and innovative co-funding models. The EATRIS translational assessment provided valuable insights in the health economics aspects of our prototype product. The expert insights, collected in a systematic, independent approach were a confirmation of our endeavor to address the most pressing medical need for the patients and allowed a consideration of development bottlenecks”.

Pim Munnik, Managing Director, Yumen Bionics

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